

COLOR THERAPY WITH CRYSTALS AND GEMSTONES

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POSITION OF CHAKRAS IN OUR BODY COLOR THERAPY WITH CRYSTALS AND STONES

What are Gems?

Gems are well-compressed small pieces found in mineral deposits found inside earth. Pearls and amber are notable exceptions in that they are formed from organic materials. Most of the gemstones are crystalline. A crystalline mineral is formed by a distinct 3-dimensional atom and this is a unique characteristic of gemstones. They possess color, hardness, aesthetic beauty, clarity and they can be cut to give sparkle. According to David Marcum's remarks in his book "The Dow Jones Irwin Guide to Fine Gems and Jewelry":

"A gemstone's origin is locked in the secrets of the formation of the cosmos. Our sun is incapable of creating, through nuclear fusion, elements that are heavier than carbon. Yet, in many stones there exist elements such as chromium, manganese, vanadium and iron. These metals which give emerald its rich green color, the ruby its dazzling red, and sapphire its serene blue, were not created in the sun's nuclear fusion cauldron. Rather they were captured during the formation of our solar system, bits of galactic debris, and the dead remnants of exploded stars and collapsed planetary systems." In today's world, the people are full of stress and strain. We all desire peace, good health and prosperity in life. In medical sciences, there are many alternatives for the control of disorders such as allopathy, homeopathy, Aayurved, yoga, Naturopathy Etc. One of these, is the GEMSTONE therapy, we are going to talk about. This is one of the most ancient & natural science followed in India million years ago. This therapy is harmless and has no side effect, and may solve many physical and psychological problems we are facing nowadays.

The function of gem therapy is associated with color energy hence it can also be called as color therapy. There is significant influence of colors like blue and red rays on the human body. Some 2000 years ago, color halls were made in many countries where patients used to take color bath for cure of their diseases. It can be said that the colors have a great influence on the system of human chemistry. But, how they exactly function is still being investigated. White light/sun light when passed through prism, radiates seven colors that can be seen clearly. The seven colors red, yellow, green, blue, violet, indigo and orange are of different wavelengths and have different effects on the system of human body. Our solar system has numerous planets, and seven planets are mainly considered in Astrological studies. there are two shadow planets also.

<u>PLANET</u>	<u>GEMSTONE</u>	<u>COLOR</u>
1) SUN/SURYA	RUBY	ORANGE
2) MOON/CHANDRA	PEARL	WHITE
3) MARS/MANGAL	CORAL	RED
4) MERCURY/BUDDHA	EMERALD	GREEN
5) JUPITER/GURU	TOPAZ	YELLOW
6) VENUS/SHUKRA	DIAMOND	WHITE
7) SATURN/SHANI	BLUE SAPPHIRE	DARK BLUE
8) RAHU		
9) KETU		

These planets represent seven chakras in our body, forming the same planetary system.as these planets affect the whole universe, these chakras are also affected by the planets, and their representative colors.These seven chakras are associated with our specific fingers.The fingers receive rays from the gemstone worn in the form of ring. These centers, although independent, are joined with the main center known as center of Saturn, which is receiver of blue color ray. Therefore, the blue color ray has the most powerful healing capacity.

HOW DOES ASTROLOGY HELP IN COLOR THERAPY

All the planets revolve around the earth at different speeds. As a result, at any moment, all the planets will have a definite position in relation to the earth and the relative position is very important which tells about the blueprint of person born during that specific time.Perfect calculations and accurate predictions based on the study of planetary position at the time of birth is the key to find out existing ailments and future health problems.

All the chakras should be in proper balance and related colors in appropriate ratio for a healthy well being.White light is present all around us,and so are the colors.to balance the ratio of colors in our body,the related gems are worn.Each finger represents a certain planet.Gemstones are therefore selected as per the need and worn in the specific finger.Sometimes,if more than two chakras are imbalanced,two gemstones are worn together,but,they should be matched well before prescribing.Gem stones and crystals can be worn as a ring,bracelet or a necklace.the above portion of our body is considered to be clean and so,the ornaments are worn likewise.

1. RED COLOR

Red color relates to ROOT CHAKRA (MOOLADHAR CHAKRA)

Red color is considered hot color and is used to stimulate the vital organs.It provides instant energy and heat.It reduces depression and stimulates appetite and warmth in body.It also depicts passionate love, danger, war etc. Red color is used to remove fatigue, colds, slow blood circulation and thus fights Anemia.

Gemstones for red color therapy:Ruby, Red Coral, Red Garnet, Poppy Jasper, Red Jasper, Red Spinel, Ruby Aura Quartz, Thulite, Rubellite (Red Tourmaline), Leopardskin Jasper, Spinel, and others

2. ORANGE COLOR

Orange color relates to SACRAL CHAKRA

Orange color denotes the color of a saint. It is a combination of fire and air elements. It stimulates warmth in body, optimism and creative part of a human being. Orange color is used for prosperity, good luck, investments, legal matters, etc. It is also used to heal muscular cramps and pain, thyroid, and large intestine ailments.

gemstones for orange color therapy: Amber, Carnelian, Fire Opal, Orange Calcite, Orange Spinel, Paraparadsha Sapphire, Peach Aventurine, Peach Moonstone, Sheelite, Sunstone, Various Jaspers and Agates

3. YELLOW COLOR

Yellow color relates to SOLAR PLEXUS CHAKRA

Yellow color relates to wisdom, ambition, science, confidence and helps to improve mental stimulation, quicker thinking. This is used to relieve stress, and relaxation. Yellow color is beneficial for healing Acne, Dermatitis, Eczema, liver problems etc.

Gemstones for yellow color therapy: Amber, Andalusite, Chrysoberyl, Citrine, Honey Calcite, Yellow Calcite, Golden Calcite, Gold, Rutiled Quartz, Yellow-Brown Scapolite, Sphalerite, Sphe, Sulfur, Sunstone, Topaz, Yellow Aragonite, Heliodor (Yellow Beryl), Yellow Carnelian, Yellow Sapphire

4. GREEN COLOR

Green color relates to HEART CHAKRA

Green color relates to nature, heart and harmony. It improves emotional balance, circulation of money, love, inner peace, youth, friends, prosperity, nature love etc. It heals blood pressure, heart problems, blood purification, increases immunity, helps building muscle, bones, and tissues.

Gemstones used for Green color therapy: Actinolite, Aventurine, Bloodstone, Diopside, Dioptase, Emerald, Green Fluorite, Green Apatite, Green Calcite, Gaspeite, Grossular Garnet, Jade, Hiddenite (Green Kunzite, Spodumene), Malachite, Maw Sit-Sit, Moldavite, Morrisonite, Moss Agate, Nephrite Jade, Peridot, Prase, Green Tourmaline, Tsavorite, Uvarovite, Variscite, Zoisite

5. BLUE COLOR

Blue color relates to THROAT CHAKRA.

Blue color relates to truth, purity, loyalty.

It is used to soothe mind, calm nature, communication skills, devotion, peaceful sleep etc. It also helps to improve communication skills and public speaking.

Blue color helps in healing joint pains, reduces fever, calms mind, and nerves. It also relieves sinus and headaches. It reduces blood pressure also. It is very helpful in treating throat problems.

Gemstones for blue color: Aqua Aura, Chinese Amazonite, Azurite, Blue Calcite, Blue Lace Agate, Blue Tiger's Eye (Hawk's Eye), Blue Topaz, Dumortierite, Blue Quartz, Kyanite, Lapis, Ocean Picture Rock, Blue Peruvian Opal, Pietersite, Blue Smithsonite, Sodalite, Sapphire, Blue Spinel, Turquoise, and others.

6. PURPLE (VIOLET) COLOR

Purple color relates to CROWN CHAKRA

Purple color relates to spiritual vision and psychic abilities.it has mystic powers. It denotes dignity, royal relations, meditaion, wisdom etc. This Color helps in healing mind and soul.It deals with mental/Emotional/Psychological Problems, Eyes, Ears, Pineal Gland, Addictions, Alcoholism, Recovery, Stimulate Spleen, Increase White Blood Cells, Decrease Pain Sensitivity, Depression.
Gemstones used for purple color therapy: Amethyst, Chevron Amethyst, Charoite, Fluorite, Lepidolite, Lavender Jade, Imperial Purple Jasper, Iolite, Tiffany Stone (Opalite), Purple Sapphire, Sugilite, Tanzanite

7. BLACK COLOR

Black color relates to ROOT CHAKRA

It denotes the earth element.It shows the urge for protection and survival.black color repels evil impacts, negative feelings.It also shows secrecy in a person's life.it opens up the unconscious mind powers. Black color heals low blood pressure and low pulse rate.

Gemstones used for black color therapy: Black Obsidian, Black Onyx, Black Tourmaline, Hematite, Black Jasper, Black Diamond, Chinese Writing Stone, Snowflake Obsidian, Black Sapphire, Rainbow Obsidian, Meteorite, Tektite, Lava Stone, Black Agate

8. WHITE COLOR

White color relates to CROWN CHAKRA

It denotes the purity of mind,body and soul.It shows balance, Light, Divinity.All the colors vibrate from whitelight.so,It also shows clean and perfect wellbeing of a person.It gives fresh feeling and higher level of spirit.It is used for developing extra sensory perceptions, i.e.,clairvoyance,clairaudience,etc.angels and spirits are dressed up in white attires.As,white color consists of all colors,it can be used in place of any color to heal up the related disease.It brings harmony and balance in life.

Gemstones used for white color therapy:Apophyllite, Calcite, Danburite, Diamond, Euclase, Goshenite (White Beryl), Quartz Crystal, Herkimer Diamond, Howlite, Moonstone, Opal, Selenite, Spodumene, White Zircon

There are many colors which are formed by the combination of these main colors.they help in healing the related mental and physical problems.

REFERENCES

V.K.JAIN, Director, *New Horizon Stone Therapy, Dehradun valley, Himalaya range, India*

Website:

Rays of Color. Healing by Color Therapy

All graphical presentations taken from net.